

Table 2. Yield data from multilocation evaluation of RR167-982 (Vandana) compared with local and improved checks. Bihar and Orissa, India, 1988-91.

Site	Vandana	Kalinga III	Birsadhan 101	Brown gora (local check)
<i>Hazaribag district, Bihar</i>				
Vigyan Kendra, Pondicherry	4.2	1.5	0.7	1.6
CRURRS	2.4	1.5	1.1	1.8
Barkatta	3.4	1.8	-	-
Handlo	2.3	1.5	-	1.2
Mean	3.2	1.6	0.9	1.5
<i>Giridih district, Bihar</i>				
Location 1	2.6	2.6	2.1	-
Location 2	1.9	1.9	1.2	1.1
Location 3	3.2	3.0	2.8	-
Location 4	4.7	3.6	4.2	-
Location 5	4.3	3.0	3.0	-
Mean	4.2	3.5	3.3	1.1
<i>Kalahandi district, Orissa</i>				
Location 1	2.9	2.6	2.7	2.5
Location 2	3.4	3.3	3.2	1.6
Mean	3.2	3.0	3.0	2.1

acceptable cooking and eating quality. It is moderately resistant to blast (BI) in uniform BI nurseries and to brown spot under field conditions. It is also resistant to sheath rot.

Vandana was evaluated under direct-seeded conditions in a station trial, multilocal testing, and in farmers' fields (Table 2) during 1988-91. It outyielded Brown gora, Birsadhan 101, and Kalinga III in grain and straw production. It averages 2.5-3.5 t/ha under normal conditions, although up to 4.7 t/ha have been recorded in farmers' fields. Vandana has also performed equally well in the highly drought-prone Kalahandi district of Orissa. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—deepwater

Performance of some promising deepwater rice (DWR) cultivars in northwestern Nigeria

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Seven lines of *Oryza sativa* and three lines of *O. glaberrima* were tested for flood tolerance and yield performance under rainfed deepwater condition at NCRI, Birnin Kebbi. Lines were evaluated against check FARO 14, which is a long-duration (170-198 d), photoperiod-sensitive variety.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. The gross plot was 4 × 3 m, and the net plot, 3.2 × 2.2 m. Two seeds per hill were sown on 17 Jun 1991 at a spacing of 20 × 20 cm.

A basal application of 30 kg NPK/ha was made at planting. Three weeks after seedling emergence, another 30 kg N/ha as urea was placed deeply among four hills before the floodwaters started in mid-July. Flood depth was recorded weekly from 16 Jul to 19 Nov. The maximum depth measured was 1.4 m on

Growth attributes and grain yield of deepwater rice cultivars.^a NCRI, Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria, 1989-91.

Cultivar	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)			Floodwater depth on weekly basis	
				1989	1990	1991	Date (1991)	cm
<i>O. glaberrima</i> ^b								
Jan-iri	99	161	389	2.2	3.0	2.4	16 Jul	7
Farin-iri	107	186	385	4.1	3.5	3.6	23 Jul	13
Yar-kaushe	101	181	388	3.0	3.3	3.3	30 Jul	18
<i>O. sativa</i>								
DM17	120	213	338	5.3	5.0	5.4	6 Aug	25
DA29	109	198	371	5.6	5.0	3.7	13 Aug	30
Maiada	109	201	361	5.4	5.5	5.4	20 Aug	47
BKN6986-17	113	190	316	4.3	5.6	2.7	27 Aug	53
FARO 4 (KAV-12)	119	200	416	2.4	3.2	3.4	3 Sep	68
							10 Sep	83
							17 Sep	100
FARO 6 (ICB)	115	220	358	3.6	2.4	4.9	24 Sep	121
FARO 7 (Mallong)	129	209	379	3.5	4.7	5.1	30 Sep	133
							10 Oct	140
FARO 14 (FRRS-43-111-2)	141	233	351	3.0	4.1	6.0	17 Oct	125
CV (%)		4.7	10.9			20.1	22 Oct	89
LSD (0.01)		18.1	ns ^c			1.63	29 Oct	75
							5 Nov	60
							12 Nov	54
							19 Nov	43

^aResults reported are 1991 data unless otherwise noted. ^bIndigenous types of rice. ^cns = not significant.

3-7 Oct. Harvesting began on 23 Oct and ended on 25 Nov.

All entries had submergence tolerance and elongation ability. Plant height, which reflects elongation ability in relation to water depth, was significantly different among entries (see table).

Tillers and panicles/m² were quite numerous, but entries did not significantly differ. *Glaberrima* cultivars had a high incidence of grain shattering,

which might be a major factor in their low grain yield.

Yields did not significantly differ among entries. None of the test entries outyielded FARO 14. This contrasts the previous year's results when DM17, DA29, and Maiada outyielded FARO 14 by producing more than 5 t/ha.

Cultivars DA29, Maiada, and *O. glaberrima* mature 3-5 wk earlier than FARO 14. The earliness of DA29 and

Maiada makes them suitable for deepwater areas where flood duration is short and the harmattan cold and wind makes cultivating long-duration varieties risky.

Their acceptability, based on phenotype and grain quality as determined with the *Standard evaluation system for rice*, is excellent. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—tidal wetlands

Netravathi (KKP-6): a promising rice variety for coastal lowlands of Karnataka, India

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Rice is grown on more than 150,000 ha in coastal Karnataka during kharif (monsoon) season. Phalguna, the variety commonly grown in lowlands that are partially submerged during heavy rains, has problems with spikelet sterility and is susceptible to neck blast (BI).

IET2886 was crossed with Red Annapurna, and KKP-6 was identified and released as Netravathi in 1990. Netravathi outyielded Phalguna (Table 1) in multilocation trials conducted at Mangalore and Brahmavar. Leaf and neck BI incidence was less in Netravathi than in Phalguna. Netravathi also resists gall midge (GM) (Table 2). It has a

Table 1. Performance of Netravathi (KKP-6) in yield trials,^a Karnataka, India, 1983-87.

Trial	Year	Location	Replications (no.)	Plot size (m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	
					KKP-6	Phalguna
GM-resistant varietal trial	1983	Agricultural Research Station, Mangalore	3	1.5 × 3.0	4.9	3.2
GM-resistant varietal trial	1984	Agricultural Research Station, Mangalore	4	4.6 × 2.0	4.4	3.5
GM-resistant varietal trial	1985	Regional Research Station, Brahmavar	4	6.2 × 1.8	4.3	4.4
Rice varietal trial	1987	Regional Research Station, Brahmavar	3	4.5 × 2.0	4.7	3.6

^aFertilized at the rate of 75-75-90 kg NPK/ha.

growth duration of about 135-140 d and is 104 cm tall. It can withstand submergence for 5-7 d.

Netravathi yields about 11% more grain than does Phalguna. Netravathi has less spikelet sterility than Phalguna, and it is suitable for parboiling. The variety is recommended for lowland areas during kharif. ■

Table 2. Reaction of Netravathi (KKP-6) to BI and GM in coastal Karnataka, India.^a

Variety	Leaf BI (% affected)	Neck BI (% affected)	GM (% affected)
Netravathi	1.3	5.1	0.00
Phalguna	3.4	24.5	0.75

^aMean of four trials.